

PROMINENT SUFIS OF BIHAR AND THEIR PERSIAN WORKS

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Abstract

Bihar has played a prominent role in the promotion of Persian language and literature in India. Sufi saints of Bihar not only contributed to Persian literature but also to the society in general. They stood for social justice and were fully imbued with a sense of humanity. It was a part of their discipline to serve the needy and the oppressed ones and they were a medium of contact between the masses and rulers thus conserving the rich socio-cultural heritage of Bihar. The great Sufis like Makhdoom Sharfuddin Maneri, Sultan Ahmad Chirmposh, Muzaffar Shams Balkhi and many have produced valuable literature and have done tremendous service for humanity in general. This Paper is an attempt to acquaint the readers of their life and works.

Key words: Sufi, Persian, Literature, Bihar

Bihar is one of the Indian states, which has played a prominent role in the promotion of Persian language and literature in India. The developmental role played in the arena of culture was carried on by Persian poets, writers and Sufis. It is quite remarkable that this particular region gave to world not only noble thinkers, reformers and humanists as Gautam Buddha, Mahavir and Ashoka but also great Sufis like Makhdoom Sharfuddin Maneri, Sultan Ahmad Chirmposh, Muzaffar Shams Balkhi and many others.

Apart from these brightest stars of Sufi galaxy, there were innumerable other Sufis who contributed to the development of Persian literature in Bihar. All of them have left behind a considerable literature in the form of Maktubat, Mulfuzat, Isharat, Aurads and other mystical tracts from which we can form an idea of their beliefs, preachings and outlook along with something that is of cultural and historical value.

Shaikh Sharfuddin Maneri is considered one of the most important revered Sufi saints of Bihar. His Maktubat-e-sadi and Maktubat-do-sadi are considered to be a best collection of letters on mystical doctrines and principles of Islam. Regarding the Malfuzats, Lataif-i-Maani, is an abridger version of Madanul-Mani, which was compiled by Zain Badr-i-Arabi, which contains the discourses delivered by Maneri.

Similarly we find Maulana Muzafar Shams Balkhi's Maktubat which contains 181 letters. His Sharah-i-Mashriq-ul-Anwar, a standard work on tradition, Sharh-i-Auida-Hafizia and a small Diwan of poems have been preserved in Khudabaksh library, Patna.

Shaikh Husain's Malfuz, entitled Ganj-i-la-Yakhfa contains his discourses of 57 Majlis and his Maktubat consists of letters on mystic subjects including one addressed to Ibrahim Shaqi of Jaunpur, a treatise in Arabic named Hazarat-i-khams (5 different planes of existence) on the problem of divine unity and his collection of mystic poems, including a Mathnavi entitled Chahar Darwesh, are more generally known, but the Futuha Khanqah of the Balkhi saints has some other works also such as Risala-i-Khair-o-Sharr, Qaza-o-Qadar, Risala-i-Muhammadiya, Aurad-i-Dah Fasli, Risala-i-Tauhid and Risala-I Akhasy-ul-Khas. (*Askari, S.H. Sufism and Sufi orders of Bihar and Bengal*)

Husain's son Shaikh Hasan Balkhi wrote small tracts such as Risala-i-maani-dhat-wajh-o-Nafs, Risala-i-Hasht, and was the compiler of Lataef-ul-Ma'ni, but his most well known work is Kashif-ul-Asrar, a commentary in Persian of his father's Arabic Risala. Husain's son Ahmad Lngar Dariya is well known because of his valuable Malfuz, Munis-ul-Qulub, which contains a mine of information about the Firdausia order of Sufis of Bihar. This Malfuz supplements the earliest works such as Manaqib-ul-Asfia, Malfuz of Maulana Amun, and Risalai-Bahram Bihari and it amplifies the references in them and gives additional information of historical and cultural value.

Bihar had such a long series and such a galaxy of Sufi mystics of the various orders that they may claim to be regarded as the home of Indian Sufism. Out of the fourteen orders or Khanwadahs those of the highest repute were represented in Bihar, and each had a share in the general spread and development of Islam in different parts of the province. There was no difference in the cardinal principles and tenets of the various orders and there was no bar to people of one order getting 'permission' (Ijazat) and 'initiation' (Bai'at) from the saints of the other orders. They differed from one another in name, sometimes in respect of garb or dress and mostly about rules and methods of meditation (Fikr) recitation (Zikr) and their attitude towards Dhikr audition (Sama) and vocal music. The Shuttaria called Madhhab or Mashrab (mode of conduct) rather than order (Khanwadah) were closely connected with the Firdausia and Suharwardia, but unlike them and the Chistia, and like the Naqshbandia, and even the Qadria, they rejected Sama, music or singing. The Shutaria and also the Madaria and Qalandaria which at one time occupied an important position in Bihar have now sunk into the background. The Naqshbandiya did not attain any vogue in early times in Bihar. the oldest and the most widely –

dispersed where the orders of the Shaharwardia and Chistiya, and though they still hold the field like the Qadriya in many parts, they were all eclipsed by the Firdausia order. In fact, owing to the towering personalities of Hazrat Sharfuddin Yahya Maneri and of his immediate successors, the Balkhi saints, the Firdausia order has always held a position of special prominence in Bihar. The saints of this 'Silsila' which was an offshoot of the great Suharwardia order constantly added to its strength and what is more important, fortunately for us they have left behind a considerable literature in the form of Makhtubat, Malfuzat, Isharat. Aurads and other mystical tracts from which we can form some idea of their beliefs, preaching and outlook and also get something that is of cultural and historical value.

The Sufis of Bihar were different from the Mullah and unlike the dry theologians or the clergy; they clung not to the letter but went to the spirit of the faith. They preferred a mystic and spiritual interpretation of the Quranic law to its mere literal sense. They considered service to God's creatures and fulfillment of their duties and responsibilities towards their fellow beings as essential for their discipline. They put aside their own desires to render themselves agreeable to all, irrespective of caste or creed and they were free from all complexes and shackles of colour and race (*Rizvi ,S.A. Muslim revivalists Movements in India, 1965*) They believed in gentle persuasion and infectious example of their character and devotion rather than in dialectics and argumentation to win others over to their side. It is the Sufis, not the mullahs who proved to be the best and most successful missionaries of Islam. They believed that a 'Kafir', unlike a 'Mushrik', could be a 'Muwahhid' (unitarian) and they quoted Ain-ul-Quzzat who said that all religions or at least a majority of them, were in essence the same.

The lives of the early Sufis of Bihar and their writings clearly show that whether they belonged to one or the other of chief orders, Chistia, Suhrawardis, Qadiria, Firdausia, Shuttaria, etc they were strictly orthodox, Bashara (with law) and not 'be shara' (without law) they followed the Quran and the Sunnat (traditions) accepted all the cardinal principles of Islam, denounced all innovations in the sphere of dogmas as Bid'at (heresy), insisted upon strict adherence to, or observance of, the obligatory duties of their faith, even attempted to reconcile religion with philosophy and tried to explain or discard all that was obviously antagonistic to the fundamental teachings of Islam. (*Askari,S.H. Islam and Muslims in Bihar, 1998*)They did not stand alone in all this, for, those who had flourished before them also did the same. Sufism came to Bihar long after it had passed through its earliest phases of development such as the ascetic and ecstatic stage followed by speculative, pantheistic and theosophical stages. Foundations had already been laid of the great Sufi orders with their hospices and monastic establishments variously called Zawiyah, Takya, Daira, Jama'atkhana and Khanqah and the great theorists and founder saints had already produced their standard works, laying down the pattern of thought which was followed by others.

The writings of Sufi saints of Bihar show that they were thoroughly acquainted with the works of master thinkers and theorists, not only of Sufism but those of other sections of the Muslims. Sufistic theosophy had already reached its highest point before its introduction in Bihar in the 13th century. (*Friedmann, Y (Ed) Islam in Asia, Vol.1.*) Maneri made use, in his own way, of what his great predecessors had written and said on the subject of Islamic mysticism and quoted from them in support of his own contention, arguments of his own. He has frequently made mention of, and given extracts from the works of such celebrated mystic writers such as Khwaja Ziauddin Abun Najib (Adabul-Mudidin), Shaikh-us-Shuyukh Shihab-uddin (Awarif), Abu Talib Makki (Quwwat-ul-Qulub), Hujjatul Islam Imam Ghazzali (Ihya-ul-ulum), wasaya) Abul Qasim-al-Qushairi (Risala), Qazi-ul-Quzzat Hamadani (Tamhidat, Zubda etc). Shaikh Abu Nasar-as-Sarraj (Allama) Mohiuddin Ibn-i-Arabi (Fususul-Hikam and Futuhat-i-Mkkia), Abdullah-al-Harith bin Asad-al-Muhasabi Basari (Muhasiba), Shaikh Abdul Qadir Jilani (Ghuniat-ul-Tlibin) and Futuhul Ghaib, Ali Bin Uthmani Jullabi Hujwiri (Kashf-ul-Mahjub). He has drawn copiously upon the classical mystic poems of Maulana Jalaluddin Rumi (Mathnavi), Khwaja Fariduddin Attar (M antiq-ul-Tir, Asrar Nama, etc) Iraqi (Lama't) Khwaja Abu Sayeed, Abul Khair (Rubayyat), Thanai, (Hadiqat-ul-haqiqah). Amir Khusro, Saadi, Khaqani and Tazkirat-ul-Aulia have been also utilized.

Persian poets of Bihar were influenced by Sufi school of thought. Sharfuddin Maneri, Ahmed Chirmposh, Muzaffar Shams Balkhi, Abul Hassan Fard, Md. Ali Habib Nasr, Sufi Maneri and a number of other Sufi poets of Bihar expressed their mystic experiences through Persian poetry. They have left behind valuable records of their precious thoughts and attitudes towards life. Mysticism has been the dominant note in the Persian poetry of Bihar in general and Sufistic poetry in particular.

Maner, Phulwarisharif and Azimabad were important locations for Sufis. Phulwarisharif has been an important seat of Persian learning. Shah Abdul Hasan Fard and Md. Habib Nasr hailed from this place. They belonged to the lineage of Hazrat Tajul Arfin Peer Mojibullah. They have left behind their Persian diwan and a number of treatises dealing with different theological problems. In poetry they have expressed their Sufistic experiences and mystic thoughts through their works (*Hussaini, S. On Sufism in India*)

Imam Taj Faqih, eleventh in direct descent from Abu Darda bin Abdul Mutallib, an uncle of the prophet of Islam, was a great theologian of Jerusalem and the ancestor and fore-runner of a long line of the Suharwardia, Shattaria and Firdausia mystic saints and missionaries of Bihar. He is said to have been induced to come in response to a call for help from an oppressed Muslim missionary. Momin Arif, and he established at Maner in 1180 A.D. as is evident from a Qita-e-Tarikh or chronogram found in some printed books, including Wasilat-us-Shraf Zaria-i-daulat etc. it says "When he became victorious over the Raja of Maner, the Imam created a new world by his justice. It has come down from the ancestors of the past; that year the faith of Mohammed was strengthened". "Din-i-Muhammad shud Qavi" is the chronogram which yields the year 576. the 'kursinama' or the genealogical table of Maner saints contains a list of the companions of the

Imam including Tajuddin Khandagah, Ali Turk Larbak and Qutb Salar, the standard bearer and general of the Imam's party who died fighting for the faith. (*Askari., S.H. Islam and Muslims in Medieval Bihar, 1998*)

The imam is reported to have gone back to Jerusalem leaving behind his three sons, Israel Ismail, and Abdul Aziz and the former's son Ismail, and Abdul Aziz, to carry on the work of the faith in both south and north Bihar. They did not bother themselves about the conquered area and its administration which is said to have been handed over to the Turks led Muhammad-bin-Bakhtiyar and his followers for, as members of the great Suharwardi order they were the missionaries of the faith and their work lay in spiritual and educational spheres. Excepting Ismail, the second son of Imam Taj Faqih, who was sent across the Ganges to North Bihar, and his son Salahuddin and grandson, Sulaiman who were opposed by, and had to fight against the Hindus, there is nothing on record or even preserved by local traditions that the descendants of the Imam had anything to do with active politics. According to the Bayaz of Mulla Taqia of Akbar's time and *Fatuh-i-Asfia*, written in 1660 only a few extracts whereof, relating to Tirhut, were copied out by the late Maulvi Ilyas of Darbhanga before the rare manuscript was destroyed in the great earthquake of 1934, Ismail lived upto the time of Alauddin Khalji and fought thrice with the Raja of Tirhut and was eventually victorious. Perhaps Mulla Taqia treally meant Ali Mardan Khalji who is said to have murdered Bakhtiyar after the latter's return from his unsuccessful expedition north of Assam and succeeded him for a time. Seventh in direct descent from Ismail was the celebrated 15th century saint of Bania Basarh near Vaishali, named Shaikh Muhammad Faizullah Qazin Bin Ola Shutari (1495), the greatest disciple of Shaikh Abdullah Shutari order in India. The saint of Mandu was fifth in direct line from Shaikh-us-Shayukh Shihabuddin Suharwardi.

The Shuttari order: Qazin bin Ola was the progenitor of a long line of saints of the Shuttari order. Of the three sons of Shaikh Qazin, Makhdam Owais Shahid, according to the *Nasab-i-Nama-i-Maner* died at the hands of a chero chief attempting to build a Mosque at Bania Basarh where he is buried. The tomb of Shaikh Abdul Rahman, the second son, is situated in Mhalla Thrayyaganj of Muzaffarpur town, and Abul Fatah Hidayatullah Sarmast, the third son worked and died at Tankol on the bank of Gandak at Hajipur. The Tankol saint (1539) was observing his 'Tai' (continuous) at the age of 14 when Sultan Husain Husain, the exiled Sharqi king of Jaunpur, paid a visit to his revered father, and he himself received the visit the devotion of emperor Humayun when the latter was in a state of war with SherShah. The fame of Shaikh Qazin, the author of *Ma'dan-ul-Asrar* and of his youngest son, Abul Fath, spread far and wide through their chief disciple, Shaikh Zahur Haji Hamid Huzur (1431) of Ratansarai in Saran. He was the spiritual guide of the two famous brothers Shaikh Phool (murdered by prince Hondal) and the renowned Muhammad Ghaus of Gwalior who died in A.H.970 and has been mentioned by Babar and Abul Fazl etc. the last was the Murshid of the scholarly and saintly Shaikh

Wajihuddin Gujrati Ahmadabad.¹ (*Singh,S Some aspects of religion and politics in Delhi Sultanate Period*) Thus the influence of Shaikh Qazin Ola traveled beyond Bihar to UP, Gujarat, M.P. and also to Punjab.among the other most notable and representative saints of the Shuttari order of Bihar,mention may be made of Shah Ali, the son of Makhdum Owais Shahid, and the founder of Jandaha, his son Shah Alauddin and the latter's great grandson Ruknuddin Abdul Bari (1705).Syed Ali Manjhan Danishmand Rajgiri, the son-in-law of Shaikh Qazin of Bania Basarh, his son, Mir Shihabuddin (1575) and the latter's famous descendants, Maulana Syed Mansur alias Mir Syed Jiw, the founder of the Rajgir madarsa and his brothers son, the celebrated PIR Syed Imamuddin, the author of many works, including Manahij-us-Shuttar (finished on 1 rajab 1115=1793)werthe other representative saints of this order. Makhdoom Shaikh Mangan and M. Shaikh Taj who lie buried in Mahanagghat, Patna city, near Mosque of Aurangazeb's time also belonged of H. Abul Fath Hadit-ullah Sarmast of Tankd.

Suharwardia and Firdausia order: Suharwardia and Firdausia order were more prominent in South Bihar. The most celebrated and earliest personalities whereof were the descendants of, or connected with, the family of Imam Taj Faqih. His eldest son, Israil and youngest Abdul Aziz, and the former's son, Makhdum Yahya Maneri and the latter's two sons Jalal Maneri and Sulaiman Langar Zamin Kakavi, were all Suharwardi saints. The father-in-law of M.Yahya Maneri and Sulaiman Kakavi, was Shihabuddin Pir Jagjot, a former Qazi of Kashghar who came to preach the faith in Bihar, settled down and died at Jethuli, on 21 september 1266, in the time of Balbun, anmd was buried at what is still known as Kachchi Dargah, on the banks of Ganges, at a short distance to the east of the old Patna city. He belonged to the Suharwardia order. Of his four saintly daughters, one was married to H.Y. Manerii, father of H.Sharfuiddin, his 3 brothers and another to Musa Hamadani, the father of the celebrated Suharwardia Amber, the disciple of Maulana Alauddin Chirmposh of Puraini (Bhagalpur district) who was himself the disciple of Maulana Sulaiman Suharwardi of Mahsya(now in Bengal). Pir Jagjot's daughter who was married to Sulaiman Langar Zamin gave birth to the famous female saint, Bibi Kamal, the mother of another important Suharwardi saint H. Husain Gharib Dhukkarposh of Tajpur, Purnea. He died on 10 safar, 892=October 1490. the fourth daughter was married to Syed Hamid Sufi, son of Adam Sufi and father of Taimullah Sufaidbaz who is buried at Bihar Sharif.

The famous Suharwardi saint, Shaikh Jalal Tabrizi, one of the chief disciples of Shihabuddin Suharwardi also came to Bihar via Delhi and Badaun and from there went to Bengal where his "Chillakhanas" are still found. Bihar also has felt the influence of the Suharwardi order through the activities of the followers of Syed Jalal Bukhari Makhdum Jahanian (d1383) and of still earlier, the celebrated H. Bahauddin Zakaria Multani. Makhdum Syed Hasan, a contemporary of Humayun and SherShah, after whom Hasanpura in Saran district is named and his sons and grandsons, Syed Ahmad of Hajipur, Syed Muhammad of Mansurganj,

¹ Singh,S Some aspects of religion and politics in Delhi Sultanate Period, The Indian History Review, Vol.31 Pg.210-20..

Patna and Syed Husain of Bhagalpur all called 'Pir Damaria' were Suharwardia saints and were linked in the chain of spiritual disciplinship to Makhdum Jahanian². Maulana Ahmad Damishqi, one of the 'Khalifas' of Bahauddin Zakaria Multani was the spiritual guide of Maulana Taquiuddin Suharwardi of Mahsum in Bengal. The last mentioned personage was the author of Multaqat, which is an abridged version of 'Ihya-ul-ulum' of the celebrated Imam Ghazzali, and he was the inspirer of many Suharwardi saints of Bihar including Yahya Maneri, the father of the renowned Makhdum Sharfuddin, the greatest Muslim saint that Bihar produced.

Sharfuddin Ahmad Maneri was the son of Maneri, a great Sufi saint who was born in Maner in 661 A.H. his pen-name being Sharaf Behari. After completion of his education, he became a disciple of Sheikh Najeebuddin of Delhi and received spiritual inspirations from him. He came to Biharsharif in 725 A.H. where he lived till the last days of his life and where he died on Thursday, the 6th, Shawal 782 A.H. besides his spiritual pursuits he was prone to literary endeavors too. He left behind him a dozen of books. Some of them are published. He was a poet and used to compose poems in Persian as well as Urdu which was then termed as Hindi or Hindustani. (*Sher.,S.A. Contribution of Bihar to Arabic, Persian and Islamic Learning, IOPSRAP, Patna 1983*)

The tomb of Makhdum Yahya Maneri is called Barhi Dargah at Maner, as distinguished from the magnificent Mausoleum of Shaikh Bayazid known as Shah Daulat; eighth in direct descent from Imam Taj Faqih through Shah Kaliluddin, a son of Shah Yahya Maneri, and called as Choti Dargah, has always been held in great veneration and was visited among others by princes and kings including Sultan Sikander Lodi and Babur. Khwaja Abdus Samad, the sister's son of Abul Fazl and Faizi, in his rare work, Akhbarul Asfia, writes "Shaikh Yahya Bin Israil, the author of Siraj-ul-Majd was one of the great personalities of his time. His grandfather (Imam Taj Faqih) came from a holy place of Khalil (Jerusalem) to Maner where he fixed up the standard of Islam and then went back to his home. Shaikh Yahya received spiritual inspiration (indirectly) from Shaikh Shihabuddin Suharwardi and Shaikh Najamuddin Firdausi (Kubra). Although he was a product of the Indian realm, yet in this very country he traversed the world of reality with his bold steps and stuck to the right path laid down by his predecessors. He perfected his spiritual experiences at Maner where he found his final resting place on 11 august 1291. Although he had reached a very advanced age and his physical strength has declined, yet for fulfilling the spiritual inspiration of God's creations he continued to seek help from the sacred teachings of the holy personages of his times." The statement of this 16th century biographer of saints that Yahya Maneri met H.Sharfuddin of Paniput and named his eldest and greatest son after him may or may not be true, but he was certainly misinformed to say that the former was a

² Askari, Op.Cit,Pg20.

ontemporary of Muhammad Tughlaq. He has himself given the correct date of Yahya's death as A.H.690. (*Askari,S.H. Islam and Muslims in Bihar, 1998*)

Next in importance was **Ahmad Chirmposh**, the saint of Amber the spiritual disciple of Shaikh Alauddin Chirmposh of Puraini (Bhagalpur) who was linked through Shaikh Sulaiman of Mahsun to the famous Maulana Taquiuddin Suharwardi of Mahsun referred to above. He according to Mr. Oldham, who writes on the authority of a manuscript by Mir Amanullah of Aurangzeb's time, was the spiritual guide of the founder of Ghazipur., the warrior-saint Syed Masud, entitled Malik-us-Saadat-i-Ghazi, the father of Syed Rajah, after whom Sarai Syed Rajah was named. The 17th century Shuttari saint, Pir Ruknuddin of Jandaha (Muzaffarpur district) tells us how Firuz Shah Tughlaq, on the occasion of his expedition to Bengal came to Bihar town, paid a visit to Ahmad Chirmposh and his cousin Ahmad Sharfuddin Yahya Maneri. The author of they rare history, *Sirat-i-Firuz Shahi* gives a detailed account of the interview between the Sultan of Delhi and H.Ahmed Chirmposh. Besides those already mentioned there were other saints of Suharwardi order who did much for the faith, had a great following in their times and still command respect of large sections of muslims in Bihar. It would suffice to mention here only two outstanding personalities of the 17th century. One was Pushto speaking Diwan Shah Arzan (d.1028=1618) of Patna who with Shaikh Husain of Lahore received the Khirqah (religious robe) and Irshad (Spiritual dirtection) from Shaikh Bahlol Qadri of Punjab but became a disciple of Shaikh Abu Turab Madani Suharwardi, on the occasion of pilgrimage to Mecca. The other Suharwardi Sufi was Maulana Muhammad Shabbaz (d.1077=1666), a great traditionalist and a founder of the long continued Madarsa or college of Mulna Chak, Bhagalpur and the spiritualk disciple of Maulana Yasin Suharwardi who lies buried in Biharsharif besides the road to Daira. The mausoleum of Mir Syed Muhammad Kan M. Bada Badesustani and the tomb of his sister's son, Shah Husain in Kaghzi muhalla are still objects of veneration ifn Biharsharif but their Silsila has become extinct. Makhdoom Bade Sustani was one of the greatest saints of Bihar and the celebrated 14th century saint. H.Sharfuddin paid annual visits to his Kauza for 12 years to offer Fatiha.

The Chistia order: A precursor of the great pioneer of the Chisti order of Sufis, the oldest Darwesh order in India, Khwaja Muinuddin of Ajmer (d.627=1230), was Syed Husain Khingsawar who according to the author of *Akhbar-ul-Asfia* and *Mirat-ul-Asrar* was appointed Governor of Ajmer but was killed in 610-1213, the year of the death of Qutbuddin Aibak, and lies buried at Tara hill, there. (*Sufi Cults, Politics and conversion: The Chistis of the Sultanate Period*) Local traditions supported by later documents Ahmad and the latter's sister's son, Syed Muhammad, called Mamoon Bhanja, died as martyrs for the faith at Jaruha, near Hajipur where their mausoleum damaged in the earthquake of 1934, was built, it is said at the instance of Shiva Singh, the Hindu Rajah of Simroan in Tithut. The mother of Naseeb (Nusrat) Shah of Bengal caused the water of "Zamzum", the holy spring of Mecca, to be brought and thrown into the well adjoining this mausoleum to sanctify its water. Rajah Man Singh Kachhawaha, when governor of Bihar, granted in 999=1590, 15 bighas of land for the upkeep of mausoleum and the facsimile of

the bilingual 'Sanad' which refers to the "Sanads granted by the previous rulers" and their verification by the deceased Sadr, Qazi Yaqub, (son-in-law of Qazi Fazilat of Sher shah's time) has been already published in Bengal past and present: Calcutta 1. traces and evidences are available of many others of 14th century who lost their lives while preaching their faith, such as Ali Sher of Bihar, Sheikh Fattu and Shaikh Burhan of Salimabad Pargana who lie buried in village Bagazer in South Bihar. Chandan Shahid, Shah Budan and Shah Shamsul Haque of Sasaram also belonged to Chistia order.

Some of the earlier Chistia saints of Bihar were Shah Mahmud Bihari and Syed Tajuddin of Dinapur, the disciples of Qutbuddin Bakhtiyar Kaki (d.633=1233), Maulana Ali Bihari, a disciple of Baba Farid Shakarganj (d.664=1265). Makhdum Adam Sufi (d.697=1297), son of Syed Ibrahim Chisti of later Hajipur (d.657=1258) and his son M.Hamiduddin (d.736=1329), a son-in-law of Shihabuddin Pirjagjot of Jethuli (derived from Ji-uthli). Makhdoom Hamiduddin Chisti's son Taimullah Sufaid Baz (d.790=1388) was the spiritual guide of his son. Faizullah of Kurji, near Dinapur (d.831=1427), of Shamsuddin alias Shah Saman of Arval (Gaya) and of Sufi Ziauddin of Chandhaus (d.821=1418), a direct descendant of the celebrated Qutbuddin Munawwar (d.760=1358) and Jamal Hanswi (d.670=1271), the great grandson of Baba Farid Shakarganj. Taimullah Sufaid Baz was married in Mahalla 'Chistiana' of Biharsharif which is adjacent to 'Bhainsasur' where lie buried a large number of Chisti saints including Ahmad Isa Taj, the younger brother of the celebrated Chistia saint, Muhammad Isa Taj of Jaunpur, a son-in-law of Syed Jalal Bukhari Makhdum Jahanian. (*Sufi Cults, Politics and conversion: The Chistis of the Sultanate Period*) An important Chisti saint of Darbhanga Makhdum Sultan Hussain who died in 815=1412.

There was a close connection between the Chisti saints of Pandua, Bengal and those of Bihar. Abdul Fattah Chisti, the founder of Qazitola in Dinapur (b.887=1482,d.993=1527), seventh from Jainair to Bihar in the time of the Khaljis. Ali Sher died fighting with the natives and he lies buried in Bihar town, but Syed Mubarak went to Bengal, became a disciple of Akhi Sirajuddin Uthman of Gaur (d.743=1342), a disciple of the celebrated Nizammuddin Aulia of Delhi, and returned to Dinapur, where he built a mosque and a Khanqah at a place where his 'Pir' had once stayed. He was followed as Qazia till the end of 17th century.

Akhi Siraj had taken from Bihar Syed Ibrahim, the young son of Jamal Aulia, a first cousin of Nizamuddin Aulia and had him married with the sister of the wife of his famous disciple and successor, Shaikh Alaul Haque of Pandua (d.786=1384) both being sisters of the Bihar saint of Choti Dargah, named H.Badr-i-Alam Badr Zahidi. Pir Badr-i-ALAM OF Junaidia order (d.844=1440) was the great grandson of Shaikh Fakhruddin Zahid (d.704=1304) and the grandson of Shaikh Shihabuddin Haqqo who was killed by the orders of Muhammad Tughlaq for denying the the justification of the titlke of Sultan-i-Adl assumed by him. Being invited by Sharfuddin Maneri he left Merath for Bihar where he arrived after the death of the great Maneri

saint in 782=1380. His descendants through the daughter of a Rajput chief are to be found in Biharsharif, Soh, Chawki in Saran district and other places in the Bihar province. He is said to have married another lady of the ruling family of Jaunpur. He is also famous in Bengal, especially among the class, whom he converted to Islam during the course of his travels in East Bengal and Chittagong and the name is invariably invoked by those in Bengal who ply their boats on the water there. One of the most revered saints of Bihar, H.Fariduddin Tawaila Bukhsh Chisti (d.897=1491), of Chandpura which has a mosque containing an inscription, dated 710, was the son of Syed Ibrahim Chisti referred to above. He was brought up at Pandua and after practicing severe austerities, became a disciple of the famous Nur Qutb Alam of Pandua (d.818=1415), the son and successor of Alaul Haque. He was sent to Bihar along with three others, including Shah Saa'dat of Benolia in Bihar Sharif and H.Ataullah Baghdadi, a descendant of the founder of Qadri order, who lies buried in Mariam Tola, Biharsharif and whose 'Silsila' is still functioning in Bihar. Sixth in direct line from Farid Tawaila Bukhsh was Diwan Abdul Wahhab (d.1096=1684) of Choti Takia, a learned and saintly personage, who converted a large number of people of what came to be known as Barahgawan. The tomb of Shah Jalal Ganj-i-Rawan is situated on Takia-i-kalan, Biharsharif. Another branch of this Chisti Silsila was represented by the saints of Daira or Barahdari. The Chisti saints of Ashrafia Khanqah of Beetho (Gaya) founded by Syed Abu Sayeed Kathanawaz, also were linked with Akhi Siraj and Alaul Haque of Pandua, Bengal, through the latter's discipline, H.Ashraf Jahangir Simnani of Kachhauchha (Faizabad, U.P.)

The Qadria Order entered Bihar in a much latter time nevertheless it was strong with chief centre at Phulwarisharif. Notable among Chisti saints were Shaikh Manjhan Kunjnashin who lies buried in mahalla Sakanut of Biharsharif and Qumais of Sadhaura where 'Takia' is situated within the fort area of the town. He was a contemporary of Akbar (*Askari, S.H. Maasir, Vol.3, Patna, 1952*). He died in Bihar on his way from Bengal to his native place, Sadhaura where his dead body was carried to be buried. But the first important personage of whom we have a contemporary account by one of his Meccan companions, Ali Sher, who lies buried at Kutumba in Aurangabad subdivision of Gaya, was Syed Muhammad of Amjhar (Gaya District), a direct descendant of the celebrated Abdul Qadir Jilani (d.1166 AD.). We learn from *Manaqib-i-Muhammadi* of Ali Sher that a Muslim missionary, named Shaikh Muhammad Ali, who was working for his faith in the wild tracts bordering on Chotanagpur division, ruled over by the Kols, was oppressed and his brother and whole family were killed by the fanatical natives on the orders of Jiwan, the Kol chief. Shaikh Ali's frantic appeals for help to the then governor of Bihar, Darya Khan Nuhani, evoked no response. He went to Mecca where his pathetic story made an impression on Syed Muhammad Qadri of Baghdad and Kolan and Domra in Aurangabad subdivision of Gaya have been mentioned as the places where the self-imposed work of preaching had resulted in a calamity. The saint came with a number of followers from the west via Multan and Surharpur in U.P. (1442-43) met Jiwan and asked him in vain to allow the work of peaceful propaganda. Excessive rain caused the demolition of the part of the mud-fort of the Kol chief who was killed and his brother, Karmun and son, Chandra also met with

their death in a miraculous manner. Hearing of a Qadri saint and of the gathering of large number of people around him, Darya Khan ordered a Kushk or villa to be built for him at a place which came to be known as 'Narahna' from the hindi saying of the saint, who disliked publicity and preferred selfless work in silence.

Shaikh Ali would not allow his followers to become ease-loving and decided to shift top another place for preaching his faith among the wild tribes. To the simple minded head 'Gwala' who had become a convert and was named Sadiq and who had expressed surprise at this move, the saint said "Namana jayyo inhan na rahna" (I do not wish to stay here: I must go). An important Qadri saint of Hajipur, Bihar, was Mulla Khwaja Bihari a disciple of celebrated Lahori saint, Miyan Mir, the spiritual guide of Prince Dara Shikoh (d.1045). he predicted the future greatness and Vizirship of the famous Sa'daullah Khan, the Prime Minister of Shahjahan. Another great but later Qadri saint of all-bihar importance was Diwan Syed Muhammad Jafar Binodpuri of Barh whose father was also saintly personage. The diwan died 1106=1694 and has left behind some works.

The Madaria Order was also strong in Bihar at one point of time. Perhaps the greatest of then four disciples of Badiuddin Madar, sometime a teacher of Husain Muiz Balkhi at Zafarabad, Jaunpur, whose mausoleum at Makanpur is still an object of veneration of both Hindus and Muslims, was the extremely pious and ascetic personage H.Jamaluddin Hurmuzi known as Jaman Jati (Yati). He lies buried at Hisla, within a domed mausoleum built in 950=1543 by Jaman Madari of Darbhanga. Shah Kangan Diwana who lies buried in Biharsharif was also a disciple of H.Shah Badiuddin Madar of Makanpur. The Madaria Qalandars who performed their devotion every year in a peculiar Indian way by walking on fire have disappeared. H.Abdul Quddus Gangohi of the 15th century writes about his 'Pir', Abdul Haque of Rudauli that the latter met some 'Majdhubans' in Bihar while he was on his way to and from Pandua, Bengal. Such distracted bare-bodied religious zealots, often referred to in early literature are not found now. (*Franklin, S The Madariya order of Sufism, OUP, Oxford, 1998.*)

Hence we find that Bihar has been a land of sufis and they have done a remarkable job in the area of promotion of peace and harmoy in that region. Since the main language of their conversation and writing had been Persian, the language has gained a lot from their contributions. A number of Maktubat and Malfuzaat were produced that are being used for the study of history and socio political scenario of their times. Persian literature in general has really been enriched by these Sufis of Bihar.

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